

BUXORODAGI SAROYLAR

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Buxoro amirlarining saroylari, ularning joylashgan o'ri. Dastlab Kogondagi saroy Buxoro shahrining ichkarisida qurilishi ko'zda tutilgani, ammo Buxoroning ko'zga ko'ringan diniy ulamolari bunga qat'iy qarshilik ko'rsatishgani haqida, buning sababi, diniy ulamolar g'ayridinlarning Buxoroga kirishlariga mone'lik qilishadi. Shundan so'ng saroy Buxorodan 12 km sharqiy qismdagi “Yangi Buxoro”, keyinchalik Kogon deb atala boshlangan shaharchada qurilishi to'g'risidagi yagona to'xtamga kelishganligi haqida ma'lumotlar bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Amir, Kogon saroyi, Mavritaniya uslubida barokko, ampir va arab usullari, Benua.

PALACES IN BUKHARA

Abstract. In this article, the palaces of Bukhara emirs, their location. It is said that initially the palace in Kogon was planned to be built inside the city of Bukhara, but prominent religious scholars of Bukhara strongly opposed it, because religious scholars prevent outsiders from entering Bukhara. After that, it was reported that they reached a single stop on the construction of the palace in the town of "New Bukhara", which was later called Kogon, 12 km east of Bukhara.

Key words: Amir, Kogon Palace, Moorish Baroque, Empire and Arabic methods, Benoit.

ДВОРЦЫ В БУХАРЕ

Аннотация. В данной статье дворцы бухарских эмиров, их расположение. Говорят, что изначально дворец в Когоне планировалось построить внутри города Бухары, однако видные богословы Бухары категорически против этого выступили, поскольку богословы не допускают в Бухару посторонних. После этого сообщалось, что они доехали до единой остановки на строительстве дворца в городе «Новая Бухара», который впоследствии стал называться Когоном, в 12 км к востоку от Бухары.

Ключевые слова: Амир, Когонский дворец, мавританское барокко, ампири и арабские методы, Бенау.

Buxoro amirining Kogondagi saroyi haqida. Buxoro amirining Kogondagi saroyi XX asr boshlarida Turkistonga rossiyalik imperatorning tashrifi munosabati bilan Sayid Abd-ad-Axad buyrug'iga asosan, rus va buxorolik ustalar tomonidan tomonidan qurilgan.

1888-yil 26-fevralda birinchi poyezd Buxoro hududiga kirib keldi. Temir yo'lining kirib kelishi, avvalo, kiborlar toifasi uchun katta xursandchiliklarga sabab bo'ldi. Buxoro amiri Sayyid Bahodir Abdulahadxon 1885-1910-yillar mobaynida Peterburg, Moskva va Qrim shaharlariga o'z oilasi, amaldorlari bilan ko'p bor sayr-sayohat qildi. Amir Yalta, Kislovodsk, Pyatigorsk, Jelesnovodsk kabi kurort shaharlardagi eng bahavo, ma'danli suvlarga boy bo'lgan yerlardan joy olib, qarorgohlarini tiklay boshladi. Shu jumladan 1894-yilda Amir Abdulahadxon o'z hududida ham, chetdan keladigan mehmonlarni munosib tarzda kutib olish maqsadida qarorgoh qurdirishga

ahd qiladi. O'z qarorgohini qurdirish g'oyasi amir Abdulahadxonga 1892-yil yaqin kishilari bilan Rusiya shaharlari bo'ylab navbatdagi sayohatga chiqqan kezlarida tinchlik bermaydi. Kavkaz, Peterburg, Moskva, Kiyev, Yalta, Bog'chasaroy, Tbilis shaharlarida bo'lib, u yerdagi rus aslzodalari hashamatli hayoti bilan tanishgan amir barcha qulayliklarga ega bo'lgan milliy va yevropacha uslubidagi muxtasham bino barpo etishlariga farmon beradi.

Dastlab saroy Buxoro shahrining ichkarisida qurilishi ko'zda tutiladi, ammo Buxoroning ko'zga ko'ringan diniy ulamolari bunga qat'iy qarshilik ko'rsatishadi. Sababi, diniy ulamolar g'ayridinlarning Buxoroga kirishlariga mone'lik qilishadi. Shundan so'ng saroy Buxorodan 12 km sharqiy qismdagi "Yangi Buxoro", keyinchalik Kogon deb atala boshlangan shaharchada qurilishi to'g'risidagi yagona to'xtamga kelishadi. Saroy qurilishini Amir Abdulahadxon o'z davrining mohir me'mori Leontiy Nikolaevich Benuaga ishonib topshiradi. Oradan qariyb 2 yil vaqt o'tgach Benua saroy loyihasini ishlab chiqib amir Abdulahadxonga ko'rsatadi. Loyihada mehmonlarni kutib olish uchun kerak bo'ladigan barcha qulayliklar ko'zda tutilgan edi: mexmonxonalar, tamaddixonalar, dam olish xonalari, yotoqxonalar, vannaxona, hashamatli kutish zallari, 2-qavatda hordiq chiqarish uchun maxsus ayvonlar Benuaning loyihasida har tomonlama puxta o'ylangan edi. Turgan gapki, loyiha amirga ma'qul bo'ladi va saroy qurilishi boshlab yuboriladi.

Sitorai Mohi Xossa Buxoro amiri saroyi. Saroy qurilishi 1895-yilda boshlanadi va u Mavritaniya uslubida barokko, ampir va arab usullari uyg'unlashgan holda buxorolik va rusiyalik mohir ustalar ishtirokida barpo qilinadi. Saroy bezaklarida asosan ganch ishlatilgan bo'lib, har bir xona o'ziga xos tarzda, yuqori mahorat bilan bezatilgan. Bino ichki va tashqi qismi bir xil, juda xam murakkab joylashuv va tuzilishga ega bo'lib, qurilish ishlarida mohir muhandis Dubrovin boshchilik qilgan. Behisob ustunlaru, katta gumbazlar va minoralar saroyni yanada ulug'vor hamda mahobatli qilib ko'rsatadi.

Saroy xonalarini ganchdan ishlangan Golland uslubida qurilgan pechlar yordamida isitishgan. Pechlar yagona sxemada ishlagan, ya'ni xona devorlari oralig'i "Barokko" italyanchadan "g'alati", "ortiqchalikka moyil" (nuqsonli marvarid) degan ma'nolarni anglatib, markazi Italiya bo'lgan XVII-XVIII asr Yevropa madaniyati xususiyati hisoblanadi. Barokko uslubi XVI asr oxiri XVII asr boshlarida so'nggi yangilanish davrida Italiyaning Rim, Mantuya Venetsiya, Florentsiya shaharlarida paydo bo'lgan. Barokko davri "g'arb sivilizatsiyasining" yuqori cho'qqisi sanalgan.

Ampir — imperiya usuli — arxitektura va amaliy san'atdagi so'nggi yuqori klassitsizm usuli. Ushbu usul Fransiyada imperator Napoleon I hukmronligi davrida paydo bo'lib, XIX asr dastlabki uch o'n yilligi davrida rivojlanib, ekletik oqimlar bilan almashgan bo'ylab havo bemalol aylanishi uchun ochiq yo'lakchalar sistemasi o'tkazilgan bo'lib, pechlardan chiqayotgan issiqlik hech qanday to'siqqa uchramay xona devorlaridagi mana shu yo'lakchalar orqali butun binoga tarqalib, xonalarni issiqlik bilan ta'minlagan. Xuddi shu devor orasidagi yo'lakchalar orqali yozgi mavsumda binoning 3 metr chuqurlikka ega yerto'la qismi tuynugi ochilib, yerto'ladagi salqin havo butun saroy xonalari bo'ylab yo'naltirilgan. Shunday qilib Benua loyihasining ushbu tahsinga sazovor qismi yordamida saroy xonalari qishda issiq va yozgi mavsumda salqin harorat bilan muntazam ravishda ta'minlanib turilgan.

Saroyning to'g'ri burchakli tarhida bo'ylama o'q bo'ylab cho'zilgan yirik zallarning biridan ikkinchisiga o'tiladi. Tarh markazida eng katta zal joylashgan. Amir davrida turli xildagi

katta yig'ilishlardan tortib, bazmlargacha mazkur zalda o'tkazilgan. Zalning devorlaridagi bo'rtma shakldagi bezaklari ganchdan mohirona qilib ishlangan. Yettita Golland pechlari xona husniga husn qo'shib, ko'rkamligini yanada oshirgan. Ushbu katta zalning pol va shift qismi almashtirilgan bo'lishiga qaramay, devordagi bo'rtma ganchkori bezaklari asl xolicha saqlangan. Har bir xona devorlaridagi anvoyi gulli bezaklardan sharqona ruh barq urib turibdi.

Binoning ikkinchi qavatiga ixcham aylanma zinapoya yordamida chiqiladi, xonalariga esa kungurador arkalar bilan bezatilgan ochiq ayvonchalar orqali o'tiladi. Ikkinchi qavatning ayvon qismida Qur'on kitobidan oyatlar arab alifbosida ganchkori bezaklar bilan gulkori qilib bitilgan. Xuddi shunday yozuvlarni binoning g'arbiy tomonidagi kirish eshigi ustida qurilgan ayvon ustunlarida xam, yog'och o'ymakorligi san'ati yordamida bezaklar berib yozilganligini ko'rish mumkin. Uchinchi qavatdan asosan zarur holatlarda xavfsizlik maqsadida foydalanilgan.

Saroyning g'arbiy eshigidan juda ham maftunkor milliy uslubdagi bezaklar bilan gulkori qilib bezatilgan xonaga kiriladi. Bu xona amirlik davrida qabulxona vazifasini bajargan bo'lib, mana bir asrdan ziyod vaqt o'tganligiga qaramay devorlardagi mohirona chizilgan naqshu nigorlar haligacha o'z jilosini yo'qotgani yo'q. Kishi ko'zini qamashtirgudek, xuddi kechagina chizilgani kabi barq urib turibdi. Xonaning sharqiy devorida Golland uslubida pech qurilgan, g'arbiy devori sal yoysimon bo'lib, ikki qavatli derazalar (vitraj) o'rnatilgan.

Saroyga jami uchta eshik orqali kirilgan bo'lib, uchalasi binoning uch tomonida joylashgan. Mohir me'mor Benua bino loyahasini shunaqa mahorat bilan ishlab chiqqanki, saroyga bir eshikdan kirgan kishi butun saroyini aylanib, mutlaqo boshqa eshik orqali chiqishi mumkin.

Keyinchalik ushbu saroydan Mang'itlar sulolasining so'nggi vakili, Abdulahadxonning o'g'li Amir Sayid Olimxon xam Buxoroga kelgan yuqori lavozimli mehmonlar uchun qarorgoh sifatida foydalangan.

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